

HOUSING PROVISION OF MILITARY PERSONNEL

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Annotation. The formation and strengthening of a strong army is directly related to the expansion of its economic and social support. In the early years of independence, social protection of military personnel became an urgent issue. This is because during this period there was a task of social protection not only for military personnel, but also for participants in World War II and the Soviet-Afghan War, as well as for citizens who served at nuclear and radiation weapons testing facilities.

Keywords: closed military camp, housing rental, head of the Housing Utilization Department, Deputy Minister of Defense for Front and Rear and Capital Construction, mortgage loan.

Introduction. Eliminating negative sentiment and distrust among the people towards the USSR army, replenishing the national army with personnel directly required a strong social protection policy. Therefore, from the first years of independence, this sphere was subjected to a process of deep reforms in order to provide social protection to military personnel. In order to provide social protection to military personnel, a policy was pursued of providing housing, free use of transport, exemption or reduction of tax payments, preferential loans for the purchase of housing and cars, and other benefits.

Research results. Since the year of independence, military personnel have been provided with housing mainly in the following manner:

1. through the privatization of state-owned housing or apartments;
2. through the establishment of closed military camps, through the renovation of existing ones;
3. through the construction (purchase) of a private dwelling or apartment;
4. through the rental of housing.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Uzbek SSR No. PF-4 dated May 7, 1990, ministries, departments and organizations were tasked with providing housing and telephones to families of disabled people and fallen servicemen of World War II in the same year. As a result, the houses and apartments belonging to the state and departments in which they lived were transferred to private property. It was decided to allocate 1,750 passenger cars from the market fund for sale to war participants and international fighters for

personal use. These benefits were also applied to those who participated in the Soviet-Afghan war and in various years in the territory of other countries¹.

At the end of 1991, the Committee on State and Public Security, Defense and Social Protection of Military Personnel considered the issue “On the work of the Tashkent city and Samarkand regional executive committees on providing military families with housing, placing them in preschool educational institutions and ensuring the employment of officers’ spouses”. As a result, the government decided to allocate additional housing for 94 apartments in the Tashkent garrison and 100 apartments in the city of Samarkand². The Samarkand regional executive committee was also tasked with allocating material resources to equip a vacant 34-apartment house in the Kattakurgan garrison.

In 2007, the total number of military personnel under contract with the Ministry of Defense was 34,133 people. However, the number of servicemen provided with housing was 20,808, and another 13,325 were in need of housing. Therefore, on September 14, 2007, in accordance with Resolution No. PQ-694, the “Regulation on providing housing to servicemen of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan” was adopted³. It developed a program for replenishing the housing stock of the Ministry of Defense through the construction of housing and the repair of family dormitories in 2007-2015⁴. According to it, a total of 5,067 housing units are planned to be created. Of these, 1,360 will be built through the construction of new housing, 574 through the repair of family dormitories, and 3,133 through the purchase of apartments. In particular, 11 servicemen were provided with housing from the city of Termez⁵.

According to the order of the Minister of Defense “On approval of the Regulation on closed military camps under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated November 16, 2013, a list of apartments in closed military camps was formed and the position of “Head of the Housing Use Department of the Ministry of Defense” was replaced by the position of “Deputy Minister of Defense for Front and Capital Construction”.

Initially, the number of apartments in closed military camps gradually increased. By the time of New Uzbekistan, the implementation of a policy of providing private housing on the basis of preferential loans led to a decrease in the number of houses and apartments in closed military camps (Appendix 16).

¹ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Kengashining axborotnomasi. № 2 (1202). 1993-yil, fevral

² O‘zMA, M-69-jamg‘arma, 1-ro‘uxat, 127-yig‘majild, 30-varaq.

³ Тинчлик ва хавфсизлигимиз обод турмушимиз кафолати / Ватанпарвар, 2013 йил 4 январ. – Б. 4.

⁴ O‘zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi Tarix instituti joriy arxivi, 2-daftar, 30-varaq.

⁵ O‘zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi Tarix instituti joriy arxivi, 2-daftar, 17-varaq.

In terms of providing military personnel with personal housing, the following changes were made in the era of New Uzbekistan:

firstly, on August 11, 2017, by the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers, a procedure was introduced for providing military personnel with long-term mortgage loans for the purchase (construction) of housing and land plots for individual housing construction⁶. According to it, it was determined that military personnel who have served for at least 5 years, have concluded a new contract, and are in need of housing will benefit from this privilege. 25% of the cost of housing was reimbursed as an initial payment. Also, the right to receive monetary compensation for renting housing for up to 24 months until the housing is handed over (the land plot is ready) was retained. In 2017, 28 housing units were put into operation, and 522 military personnel were provided with housing. In February-March 2018, another 720 military personnel were given new houses. By the end of 2024, about 30 thousand military personnel were fully provided with housing⁷;

Secondly, according to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 2025 No. PQ-71, from June 1, 2025, the initial payment for obtaining a mortgage loan for the purchase (construction) of housing for military personnel who have served more than ten years of military service in the calendar year was set at 35 percent of the cost of housing⁸;

However, even during this period, some problems remained in providing housing. In particular, it was decided to build a total of 100 multi-storey housing units in 2018. However, the start of this work was delayed for various reasons. The Head of State, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, expressed his critical opinion on this issue as follows: “Unfortunately, in this matter, not all leaders fully understand the meaning and importance of the given task. As a result, the launch of this project dragged on for several months for no reason, and I had to deal with this issue personally.”⁹

Payments related to housing rent also play an important role in the implementation of social security policy in the defense system. This issue was initially regulated by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of July 25, 2005 “On the Procedure for Payment of Monthly Monetary Compensation for Renting Housing to Military Personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan”. According to it, monthly monetary compensation payments were

⁶ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами. № 33 (619). 2017 йил 21 август.

⁷ O'zbekistonda havo hujumidan mudofaa bo'yicha yangi bo'linmalar tashkil etiladi — Daryo Yangiliklari

⁸ <https://www.lex.uz/docs/-7399907>

⁹ Мирзиёев Ш.М. Халқимизнинг розилиги бизнинг фаолиятимизга берилган энг олий баҳодир. 2-жилд. — Тошкент: Ўзбекистон НМИУ, 2018. — Б. 165.

established for renting housing for military personnel: in Tashkent - up to 4 times the base calculation amount, in Nukus and regional centers - up to 3 times, in other cities, district centers and settlements - up to 2 times. In the case of three or more family members (excluding the military personnel themselves), the amounts of this monetary compensation were increased by 50 percent¹⁰. In order to prevent misuse of allocated funds, a procedure for submitting a lease agreement with notarization was introduced in accordance with the resolution of April 17, 2012¹¹.

By the time of New Uzbekistan, a number of positive changes were also made in issues related to renting housing for military personnel:

firstly, the introduction of unified interactive services in all areas facilitated the execution of a housing lease agreement. In particular, the remote execution of the lease agreement through tax offices or the tax platform saved military personnel time and money spent on notarial documents;

secondly, according to Resolution No. PQ-71 dated February 24, 2025, the amount of monthly monetary compensation paid for renting a dwelling was increased by 20% from March 1, 2025¹². That is, monthly monetary compensation payments for renting a dwelling were established in the city of Tashkent - up to 4.8 (2,025,000 soums) of the base calculation amount, in the city of Nukus and regional centers - up to 3.6 (1,350,000 soums), in other cities, district centers and settlements of the republic - up to 2.4 (900,000 soums). Also, starting from 2026, a procedure has been introduced for determining the amount of monthly cash compensation payments annually by resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers, based on market prices for housing rent in the regions.

In conclusion, it can be noted that during the years of independence, reforms in the provision of temporary or personal housing for military personnel were implemented gradually. Since the state mechanism for providing military personnel with housing was not formed in sufficient capacity in the first five years, the demand for housing was partially met through the renovation of buildings and structures owned by the state and departments, as well as the construction of new facilities. The introduction of compensation payments for military personnel for renting housing since 2005 was an important step in the development of this area. It is of particular importance that the number and order of family members were also taken into account. However, the issue of ownership of personal housing during the retirement period of military

¹⁰ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами. № 25-26 (112). 2005 йил 30 июн.

¹¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами. № 16 (113). 2012 йил 17 апрел

<https://www.lex.uz/docs/-7399907>

personnel remained relevant. As a result of the reforms carried out during the period of New Uzbekistan, the demand for housing was met by reducing the use of state and agency-owned housing and apartments, providing private housing or covering the cost of temporarily renting a place with the necessary amenities based on personal needs.

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